

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

TRANSFORMATION OF ATTITUDES TOWARDS HISTORICAL MONUMENTS IN UZBEKISTAN (ON THE EXAMPLE OF KASHKADARYA REGION)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6528656>

Odilova Fayoza Odil qizi

Samarkand State Institute of Architecture and Construction

She is an intern at the Department of Theory and History of Architecture

Annotation: *The museum is a scientific and educational center for the collection, preservation, study and promotion of historical, material and spiritual monuments, and carries out propaganda and educational work through its expositions and exhibitions. In 1996, the State Museum of the History of the Timurids was established in various cities of the country, including Tashkent, the Museum of the Memory of the Victims of Repressions in 2002, and the Museum of Archeology in Termez.*

Key words: *The State Museum of History of Uzbekistan, the State Museum of Art of Uzbekistan and a number of regional museums have been reconstructed.*

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov No. PF-1913 of January 12, 1998 "On radical improvement and enhancement of the activities of museums" is a long-awaited document of museologists, which opened the way for the development of museology. One of the goals of the decree was to unite all the museums in the country into a single system, that is, to create a central governing body that would manage them spiritually. According to the Decree, from the first days of its existence, the newly established Uzbekmuseum Foundation has defined its main directions and tasks to be implemented.

These days, our museologists have developed a special scientific concept for the development of museums in order to further improve the activities of museums in the country. According to experts, the scientific concept of the new exposition of the State Museum of History of Uzbekistan can serve as a model for all museums. Now the concept and thematic-exposition plans have been reproduced and distributed to all museums in the country. In recent years, a number of measures have been taken to radically improve the work of museums. In particular, on May 16, 2002, the Republican Museum "Uzbekmuseum" held a scientific-practical conference on "Museums of Uzbekistan in the XXI century." Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 07 / 105-282 of June 11, 2002

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

"On studying the state of equipping museums based on the idea of national independence and providing them with assistance in this regard" is aimed at studying the activities of all museums in the country. According to this document, the Uzbekmuseum Foundation has established a working group with the participation of a group of leading specialists, scientists and museologists. Museums, as some have imagined, are not just a "spreading market", a house built by collectors to collect the heritage of our ancestors, but also a sacred place designed to provide accurate information about the history of a particular period and a particular exhibit. The new computer center "Open Treasure" in the Bukhara Museum Reserve has the opportunity to create its own website on the Internet and deliver the system of exhibits stored in the museum fund to all countries of the world. This, of course, will serve to establish this museum's cooperation with museums around the world. If all the heads of museums in the country work in a scientific and methodological direction that fully meets today's requirements and further improve the work of the museum in the spirit of the ideas of national independence, the existing problems will gradually be resolved.

On August 31, 1991, the Uzbek people achieved the long-awaited Independence. As in all spheres of our life, great historical changes have taken place in the activities of museums. In accordance with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of April 21, 1992, the State Museum of History of Uzbekistan was reorganized. In essence, the modern and national museum was founded on this date, and the Decree of President Islam Karimov "On radical improvement and enhancement of the activities of museums" (January 12, 1998) marked a turning point in the development of our museums. Today, the State Museum of History of Uzbekistan is one of the largest scientific and educational centers, which has about 250,000 exhibits. Among them are many valuable collections on numismatics, archeology, ethnography, and ethnography. The new exposition of the State Museum of History of Uzbekistan is aimed at demonstrating the development of historical and cultural processes in the territory of Uzbekistan from ancient times to the present day through material evidence and visual aids. With a total area of about two thousand square meters, occupying the third and fourth floors of the building, this exposition houses about ten thousand exhibits. They reflect the history of the formation of the Uzbek statehood, the rich traditions and culture of the Uzbek people. The exhibits depicting the period of the primitive regime in the first exposition testify to the fact that the territory of Uzbekistan is one of the oldest centers of Eastern civilization. The establishment of production on the basis of agriculture and animal husbandry, socio-economic changes, the development of

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

handicrafts on the basis of basic chemical and technological knowledge, the establishment of Zoroastrianism in the development of religious thought, cultural relations with highly developed centers of the ancient East, castles and early cities. emergence played a major role in the formation of large states. Agriculture and

Information about the peculiar development and interdependence of animal husbandry, the struggle of the peoples of Uzbekistan against the Achaemenids, Greco-Macedonians and Sassanids, Khorezmians, Bactrians, the Fergana state and the Kushan Empire is also very well covered. The objects displayed in the halls are distinguished by the diversity of their content, which embodies the high culture of our ancestors in the first millennium BC and the first millennium AD. Many of these are invaluable examples of world culture and art. Wall inscriptions, sculptural images, architectural works related to the Buddhist theme have a special place in the exposition. The great medieval cultural heritage of the Uzbek people is also reflected in the exposition. In particular, in the exposition dedicated to the period of Timur and the Timurids, you can see many exhibits that tell the story of the high level of development of science and culture as a result of the efforts of Amir Temur. The high level of development of handicrafts in the XVIII-XIX centuries is reflected in the exposition of ceramics, carvings, Bukhara velvet and adras, as well as gold embroidery. The further development of our country, in particular, the struggle for freedom during the colonial period, the struggle of our enlighteners for the enlightenment, prosperity and liberation of their homeland are vividly demonstrated through maps, paintings and paintings.

The last exposition of the museum is dedicated to the great political, economic and social achievements of the newly independent Republic of Uzbekistan in a short period of time. For almost 12 years, Uzbekistan has become one of the countries that has found its rightful place in the world. In other words, the integration of historical development and cultural development is reflected in the museum media as a whole history of the nation. Today, the State Museum of History of Uzbekistan, one of the largest scientific and cultural centers, has created an objective history of the Uzbek people. But when we see in countless museums the countless and rare monuments that were once carried away from our homeland, the regrets and aspirations of our hearts scratch our hearts. Man comes into the world once. And the goodness created by him will never be forgotten. Because goodness is eternal. After all, we, like our ancestors, must leave a worthy legacy to future generations. As President Islam Karimov said: "Our children and future generations will feel the same gratitude for us as we feel for our great

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

ancestors, so that future generations will accept this land, this sacred land, rich, strong and powerful. It is our civic duty to do whatever it takes to make them feel.
”

REFERENCE:

Saydalievich U. S., Abdurashid ogli A. S., Qurbonboy ogli X. J. UNDERSTANDING AND CONCEPTING BALLS IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY PATRIOTISM //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 9. – №. 12. – С. 924-929.

Saydalievich, Ubaydullaev Saidakbar, Abdulhakimov Shahzodbek Abdurashid ogli, and Xofizov Javohirbek Qurbonboy ogli. "UNDERSTANDING AND CONCEPTING BALLS IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY PATRIOTISM." Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal 9.12 (2021): 924-929.

Saydalievich, U. S., Abdurashid ogli, A. S., & Qurbonboy ogli, X. J. (2021). UNDERSTANDING AND CONCEPTING BALLS IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY PATRIOTISM. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 9(12), 924-929.

Khalilovich M. S., Saydaliyevich U. S., Ogli A. O. M. EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY AND PATRIOTISM //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 2. – С. 572-574.

Khalilovich, Mamajanov Soyibjon, Ubaydullayev Saidakbar Saydaliyevich, and Abdulpattoyev Orifjon Muxiddin Ogli. "EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY AND PATRIOTISM." Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal 10.2 (2022): 572-574.

Khalilovich, M. S., Saydaliyevich, U. S., & Ogli, A. O. M. (2022). EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY AND PATRIOTISM. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(2), 572-574.